

Technical Guideline Series

Contents

Part 7 - How to Cite IPBES Assessment Reports	3
I. Business and Biodiversity Assessment	4
Full report	4
Summary for policymakers	4
Chapter 1	4
Chapter 2	4
Chapter 3	5
Chapter 4	5
Chapter 5	5
Chapter 6	5
II. Transformative Change Assessment	6
Full report	6
Summary for policymakers	6
Chapter 1	6
Chapter 2	7
Chapter 3	7
Chapter 4	7
Chapter 5	7
III. Nexus Assessment	8
Full report	8
Summary for Policy Makers	8
Chapter 1	8
Chapter 2	9
Chapter 3	9
Chapter 4	9
Chapter 5	9
Chapter 5.0	10
Chapter 5.1	10
Chapter 5.2	10

Chapter 5.3	11
Chapter 5.4	11
Chapter 5.5	11
Chapter 5.6	11
Chapter 6	12
Chapter 7	12
IV. Invasive Alien Species Assessment	12
Full report	12
Summary for Policy Makers	12
Chapter 1	13
Chapter 2	13
Chapter 3	13
Chapter 4	14
Chapter 5	14
Chapter 6	14
V. Sustainable Use Assessment	14
Full report	14
Summary for Policy Makers	15
Chapter 1	15
Chapter 2	15
Chapter 3	15
Chapter 4	16
Chapter 5	16
Chapter 6	16
VI. Values Assessment	16
Full report	16
Summary for Policy Makers	17
Chapter 1	17
Chapter 2	17
Chapter 3	17
Chapter 4	18
Chapter 5	18
Chapter 6	18
VII. Global Assessment	19
Full report	19
Summary for Policy Makers	19

Chapter 1	19
Chapter 2.1	19
Chapter 2.2	20
Chapter 2.3	20
Chapter 3	20
Chapter 4	20
Chapter 5	21
Chapter 6	21
VIII. Regional Assessment for Africa	21
Full report	21
Summary for Policy Makers	21
IX. Regional Assessment for the Americas	22
Full report	22
Summary for Policy Makers	22
X. Regional Assessment for Asia and the Pacific	22
Full report	22
Summary for Policy Makers	22
XI. Regional Assessment for Europe and Central Asia	23
Full report	23
Summary for Policy Makers	23
XII. Land degradation Assessment	23
Full report	23
Summary for Policy Makers	23
XIII. Pollinators Assessment	24
Full report	24
Summary for Policy Makers	24
XIV. Scenarios and Models Assessment	24
Full report	24
Summary for Policy Makers	24

Part 7 - How to Cite IPBES Assessment Reports

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This technical guideline is a resource for everyone to cite previous IPBES assessments starting with the IPBES Global Assessment. BibTeX and RIS files are available to download beneath each citation. Assessments approved at each future Plenary session will be added to the list. Suggested citations are created by the assessments.

I. Business and Biodiversity Assessment

Full report Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185116>

IPBES (2026). Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185116>

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Summary for policymakers Summary for policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature’s Contributions to People DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369060>

IPBES (2026). Summary for policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature’s Contributions to People. Jones M., Polasky S., Rueda X., Brooks S., Carter Ingram J., Egoh B. N., von Hase A., Kohsaka R., Kulak M., Leach K., Loyola R., Mandle L., Rodriguez-Osuna V., Schaafsma M. and Sonter L. J. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369060>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Setting the scene DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074175>

Rodriguez Osuna, V., Ingram J.C., Budiani I., de Jesus E., Inostroza L., Kalumanga Ngallaba E., Perram A., Schultz L., Shimshack J., Teren G., Ayambire R., Priyadarshini P. (2026). Chapter 1: Setting the scene. In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature’s Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074175>

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Chapter 2 Chapter 2: How does business depend on biodiversity? DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074303>

Egoh B.N., Schaafsma M., Duan H., Hochard J., Joo W., López Cubillos S., Paspaldzhiev I., Prodanova H., Willemsen L., Koh N.S., Lankia T., Vargas O. (2026). Chapter 2: How does business depend on biodiversity? In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature’s Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074303>

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Chapter 3 Chapter 3: How does business impact biodiversity? DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074410>

Mandle L., Koshaka R., Bull J., Crona B., Johnson M.A., Oguge N.O., Panwar R., Romero C., Ávila Ortega D.I., Chelangat S. Chetty K., Vargas O. (2026). Chapter 3: How does business impact biodiversity?. In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
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Chapter 4 Chapter 4: Approaches for measurement of business dependencies and impacts on biodiversity DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074500>

Brooks S., Kulak M., Feger C., Lee H., van Oorschot M., Pavani B.F., Pfister S., Verones F., Zanetti E.A., Bedford J., Nemecek D., Vera Paz A. (2026). Chapter 4: Approaches for measurement of business dependencies and impacts on biodiversity. In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
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Chapter 5 Chapter 5: Businesses as key actors in transformative change: options for action DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074573>

von Hase A., Sonter L.J., Nguyen T., Adam J., Dickinson S., Enrici M-H., Fabregas T., Howard P., Hummel Wicher N.L., Husain H.J., Lasmana F.P., Narain D., Vera Paz A., Tarasova-Krasiieva, O., Vargas, O. (2026). Chapter 5: Businesses as key actors in transformative change: options for action. In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074573>

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6: Creating an enabling environment for business: options for action by governments, the financial sector, Indigenous people and local communities and civil society DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074600>

Leach K., Loyola R., Chatwin A., Leenders C., Mukumbuta Guillemin I., Park M.S., Syed Hazari S.M., Yiu E. Prodani K., Rabeschini G., Vera Paz A. (2026). Chapter 6: Creating an enabling environment for business: options for action by governments, the financial sector, Indigenous people and local communities and civil society. In: Methodological Assessment Report of the

Impact and Dependency of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
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II. Transformative Change Assessment

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Summary for policymakers Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382230>

IPBES (2024). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., Agrawal, A., Bennett, E., Biggs, O., Calderón Contreras, R., Carr, E., Frantzeskaki, N., Gosnell, H., Gurung, J., Lambertucci, S., Leventon, J., Liao, C., Reyes García, V., Shannon, L., Villasante, S., Wickson, F., Zinngrebe, Y., and Perianin, L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382230>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Transformative change and a sustainable world DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382238>

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Chapter 2 Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382240>

Villasante, S., Shannon, L., Liao, C., Betemariam, E., Cunningham, S., Ellis, E., Hausner, V., Huang, Q., Mannetti, L., Otero, I., Piñeiro, G., Prasad Gautam, A., Waddock, S., Wheeler, H., Fouqueray, T., Karasov, O., Tasse Taboue, G., Mazzeo, N., Mishra, A., and Guibal, C. (2024). Chapter 2: Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., and Agrawal, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382240>

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Chapter 3 How transformative change occurs DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382244>

Bennett, E., Biggs, O., Calderón Contreras, R., Golden Kroner, R., Vianna Mansur, A., Woroniecki, S., Acar, S., Aksoy, Z., Alpizar, F., Lam, D., Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Linnér, B.-O., Mehta, L., Campos, C., Nishi, M., Rahiri, N., Richardson, M., Sabinot, C., Simão Seixas, C., Stokland, H., Balvanera, P., Chan, K., Guibal, C., and Garibaldi, L. (2024). Chapter 3: How transformative change occurs. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., and Agrawal, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382244>

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Chapter 4 Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change towards a sustainable world DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382246>

Frantzeskaki, N., Lambertucci, S., Carr, E., Dempsey, J., Karamidehkordi, E., Sengupta, A., Rojas Marchini, F., Vogel, C., Andriamahefazafy, M., Boonstra, W., Espinoza-Cisneros, E., Garcia, K., Morita, K., Nelson, V., Ojeda, D., Plieninger, T., Stirling, A., Tokunaga, K., Chen, R., Metzger, J.-P., Smith, P., and Guibal, C. (2024). Chapter 4: Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change towards a sustainable world. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., and Agrawal, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382246>

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Chapter 5 Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382248>

Gosnell, H., Reyes-García, V., Zinngrebe, Y., Almeida Magris, R., Benessaiah, K., Bonilla-Moheno, M., Chandipo, R., Claudet, J., Gemmill-Herren, B., Goldstein, B., Huntjens, P., Ifejika

Speranza, C., Nakao, F., Pandit, R., Pereira, L., Raab, K., Soares, T., Titttonell, P., Guo, X., Miwa, K., Joly, C., Zaccagnini, M., Guibal, C., and Garibaldi, L. (2024). Chapter 5: Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., and Agrawal, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382248>

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III. Nexus Assessment

Full report Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850054>

IPBES (2024). Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850054>

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Summary for Policy Makers Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850289>

IPBES (2024). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Harmáčková, Z. V., Hayman, D. T. S., Herrero, M., Kumar, R., Ley, D., Mangalagiu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Pengue, W. A., Prist, P. R., Ricketts, T. H., Rounsevell, M. D. A., Saito, O., Selomane, O., Seppelt, R., Singh, P. K., Sitas, N., Smith, P., Vause, J., Molua, E. L., Zambrana-Torrel, C., and Obura, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850289>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Introducing the nexus DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850293>

Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P., Phang, S. C., Zambrana-Torrel, C., Enrico, L., Giraudoux, P., Jarvis, R. M., Karim, P. G., Rivera Ferre, M. G., Luque, S., Prescott, G. W., Sietz, D., Turetta, A. P. D., and Obura, D. (2024). Chapter 1: Introducing the nexus. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850293>

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Chapter 2 Chapter 2: Status and past trends of interactions in the nexus DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850301>

Prist, P. R., Seppelt, R., Hayman, D. T. S., Molua, E. L., Arneth, A., Biber-Freudenberger, L., Bukvareva, E., Chaudhary, S., Dubey, P. K., Földvári, G., Godoy-Faúndez, A., Fischer, J., Howe, C., Hussain, A., Lorilla, R. S., Maire, E., Materu, S. F., Miyake, Y., Türkmen, A., and Vanham, D. (2024). Chapter 2: Status and past trends of interactions in the nexus. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, German DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850301>

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Chapter 3 Chapter 3: Future interactions across the nexus DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850303>

Harmáčková, Z. V., Rounsevell, M. D. A., Selomane, O., Awuku-Sowah, E. M., Budiharta, S., Coll, M., Hales, S., Jung, M., Kumar, P., Leclère, D., Metaxas, A., Meirelles Oliveira, B., Nyelele, C., Owuor, M. A., Popp, A., Rashleigh, B., Thomas, S. M., Tsuchiya, K., Villamor, G., and Yue, T. X. (2024). Chapter 3: Future interactions across the nexus. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850303>

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Chapter 4 Chapter 4: Policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus that could facilitate and accelerate the transition to a range of sustainable futures DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850305>

Mangalagiu D., Saito, O., Sitas, N., Dias, A. C. E., Felipe-Lucia, M. R., Filyushkina, A., Ghosh, S., Gonçalves, L. R., Hiwasaki, L., Kok, M. T. J., Lynch, A. J., Machado, M. R., Ometto, J. P., Pires, A. P. F., Rhodes, J. R., Vallet, A., and Xie, L. (2024). Chapter 4: Policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus that could facilitate and accelerate the transition to a range of sustainable futures. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850305>

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Chapter 5 Chapter 5: Options for delivering sustainable approaches DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850309>

Ricketts, T. H., Herrero, M., Smith, P., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Kumar, R., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Singh, P. K., Lavorel, S., Aboubakrine, M. W. M., Aguiar S., Akamani, K., Benedek, Z., Campbell, D., Castro-Díaz, R., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Cherubini, F., das Neves, C. G., De La Cruz, P., Díaz-José, J., Dunnett, S., Santos, M. J., Gupta,

H., Gyawali, D., Handa, C., Hill, S., Hori, M., Ito, A., Joshi, G. R., Keune, H., Khan, S., Koltz, A. M., Kouame, A. A., Kuiken, T., Lalika, M., Lee, K.-C., Llope, M., Mácová, K., Melo, F., Milano, F. A., Minaverri, C. M., Morand, S., Mustafa, M. A., Oinonen, S., Raza, N., Rai, K. K., Reuben, R. C., Rosado-May, F. J., Samoilys M., Sandin, L., Simatele, M. D., Sivadas, D., Spierenburg, M., Tirado, M. C., Twongyirwe, R., Vale, M. M., Williams, D. R., Xu, X., and van Huysen, T. L. (2024). Chapter 5: Options for delivering sustainable approaches. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850309>

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Chapter 5.0 Chapter 5.0: Options for delivering sustainable approaches - Introduction DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850315>

Ricketts, T. H., Herrero, M., Smith, P., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Kumar, R., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Singh, P. K., and van Huysen, T. L. (2024). Chapter 5.0: Options for delivering sustainable approaches – Introduction. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850315>

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Chapter 5.1 Chapter 5.1: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to biodiversity conservation, restoration and sustainable use DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850321>

Alonso Roldán, V., Lavorel, S., Aguiar S., Akamani K., Dunnett, S., Handa, C., Hill, S., Lee, K.-C., Mácová, K., Melo, F., Rai, K. K., Samoilys M., and Sivadas, D. (2024). Chapter 5.1: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to biodiversity conservation, restoration and sustainable use. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850321>

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Chapter 5.2 Chapter 5.2: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to water DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850325>

Kumar, R., Pauker, C., Santos, M. J., Gyawali, D., Kouame, A. A., Lalika, M., Minaverri, C. M., Oinonen, S., Raza, N., Sandin, L., and Simatele, M. D. (2024). Chapter 5.2: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to water. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850325>

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Chapter 5.3 Chapter 5.3: Options for delivering sustainable food systems DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850331>

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Chapter 5.4 Chapter 5.4: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to health DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850335>

McFarlane, R. A., Dasgupta, P., Aboubakrine, M. W. M., das Neves, C. G., De La Cruz, P., Keune, H., Koltz, A. M., Kuiken, T., Morand, S., and Reuben, R. C. (2024). Chapter 5.4: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to health. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850335>

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Chapter 5.5 Chapter 5.5: Options for delivering biodiversity-related approaches to climate change, adaptation and mitigation, including relevant aspects of the energy system DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850339>

Singh, P. K., Smith, P., Cherubini, F., Díaz-José, J., Duchková, H., Gupta, H., Hori, M., Ito, A., Khan, S., Llope, M., Tirado, M. C., Vale, M. M., and Xu, X. (2024). Chapter 5: Options for delivering sustainable biodiversity-related approaches to climate change, adaptation and mitigation, including relevant aspects of the energy system. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850339>

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Chapter 5.6 Chapter 5.6: Options for delivering sustainable approaches - Synthesis DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850345>

Ricketts, T. H., Herrero, M., Smith, P., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Kumar, R., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., and Singh, P. K. (2024). Chapter 5.6: Options for delivering sustainable approaches – Synthesis. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850345>

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6: Options for delivering sustainable approaches to public and private finance for biodiversity-related elements of the nexus DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850349>

Vause, J., Ley, D., Pengue, W. A., Cavanagh, C. J., Eriksen, S. H., Kharrazi, A., Pacheco, A., Ahmed, I., Cisneros-Montemayor, A., De Palma, A., Glavovic, B. C., Iiyama, M., King-Okumu, C., Platais, G. H., Reda, F., Sangha, K. K., Schumacher, K., Tormáné Kovács, E., and Wong, G. Y. (2024). Chapter 6. Options for delivering sustainable approaches to public and private finance for biodiversity-related elements of the nexus. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Harrison, P. A., McElwee, P. D., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850349>

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Chapter 7 Chapter 7: Summary and synthesis of options, knowledge and technology gaps and capacity development DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850355>

McElwee, P. D., Sitas, N., Ley, D., Glavovic, B. C., Herrero, M., Biber-Freudenberger, L., Campbell, D., Cavanagh, C. J., Cherubini, F., Dasgupta, P., Eriksen, S. H., Harrison, P. A., Jarvis, R. M., Kuiken, T., Luque, S., Lynch, A. J., Mangalagiu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Phang, S. C., Prist, P. R., Rounsevell, M. D. A., Samoilys, M., Sangha, K. K., Selomane, O., Sietz, D., Smith, P., Spierenburg, M., Vallet, A., Williams, D. R., and Xie, L. (2024). Chapter 7: Summary and synthesis of options, knowledge and technology gaps and capacity development. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., and van Huysen, T. L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850355>

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IV. Invasive Alien Species Assessment

Full report Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430682>

IPBES (2023). Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430682>

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Summary for Policy Makers Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430692>

IPBES (2023). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., Renard Truong, T., Bacher, S., Galil, B. S., Hulme, P. E., Ikeda, T., Sankaran, K. V., McGeoch, M. A., Meyerson, L. A., Nuñez, M. A., Ordonez, A., Rahlao, S. J., Schwindt, E., Seebens, H., Sheppard, A. W., and Vandvik, V. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430692>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Introducing biological invasions and the IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430723>

Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., Renard Truong, T., Lipinskaya, T., and Vicente, J. R. (2023). Chapter 1: Introducing biological invasions and the IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430723>

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Chapter 2 Chapter 2: Trends and status of alien and invasive alien species

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Seebens, H., Meyerson, L. A., Rahlao, S. J., Lenzner, B., Tricarico, E., Aleksanyan, A., Courchamp, F., Keskin, E., Saeedi, H., Tawake, A., and Pyšek, P. (2023). Chapter 2: Trends and status of alien and invasive alien species. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430725>

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Chapter 3 Chapter 3: Drivers affecting biological invasions

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Hulme, P. E., Ikeda, T., Vandvik, V., Blanchard, R., Camacho-Cervantes, M., Herrera, I., Koyama, A., Morales, C. L., Munishi, L. K., Pallewatta, P. K. T. N. S., Per, E., Pergl, J., Ricciardi, A., and Xavier, R. O. (2023). Chapter 3: Drivers affecting biological invasions. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430727>

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Chapter 4 Chapter 4: Impacts of invasive alien species on nature, nature’s contributions to people, and good quality of life

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Bacher, S., Galil, B. S., Nuñez, M. A., Ansong, M., Cassey, P., Dehnen-Schmutz, K., Fayvush, G., Hiremath, A. J., Ikegami, M., Martinou, A. F., McDermott, S. M., Preda, C., Vilà, M., Weyl, O. L. F., Fernandez, R. D., and Ryan-Colton, E. (2023). Chapter 4: Impacts of invasive alien species on nature, nature’s contributions to people, and good quality of life. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430731>

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Chapter 5 Chapter 5: Management; Challenges, Opportunities and Lessons Learned

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Sankaran, K. V., Schwindt, E., Sheppard, A. W., Foxcroft, L. C., Vanderhoeven, S., Egawa, C., Peacock, L., Castillo, M. L., Zenni, R. D., Müllerová, J., González-Martínez, A. I., Bukombe, J. K., Wanzala, W., and Mangwa, D. C. (2023). Chapter 5: Management; Challenges, Opportunities and Lessons Learned. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430733>

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6: Governance and policy options for the management of biological invasions

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McGeoch, M. A., Ordonez, A., Howard, P. L., Groom, Q. J., Shrestha, B. B., Fernandez, M., Brugnoli, E., Bwalya, B., Byun, C., Ksenofontov, S., Ojaveer, H., Simberloff, D., Mungi, N. A., and Rono, B. (2023). Chapter 6: Governance and policy options for the management of biological invasions. In: Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430747>

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V. Sustainable Use Assessment

Full report Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

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IPBES (2022). Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (1499 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448567>

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Summary for Policy Makers Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6425599>

IPBES (2022). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (35 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., Kieling, D., Balachander, G., Barron, E. S., Chaudhary, R. P., Gasalla, M., Halmy, M., Hicks, C., Park, M. S., Parlee, B., Rice, J., Ticktin, T., and Tittensor, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6425599>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Setting the scene

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Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Hallosserie, A., Michaud-Lopez, C. E., Parma, A., St. Martin, K., and Stockland, H. (2022). Chapter 1: Setting the scene. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (78 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6425671>

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Chapter 2 Chapter 2: Conceptualizing the sustainable use of wild species

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Rice, J., Ticktin, T., Díaz -Reviriego, I., Furukawa, T., Gandiwa, E., Lavadinović, V., Margayan, L., Pascua, P., Sathyapalan, J. Akachuku, C., and Hallosserie, A. (2022). Chapter 2: Conceptualizing the sustainable use of wild species. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (138 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6053970>

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Chapter 3 Chapter 3: Status of and trends in the use of wild species and its implications for wild species, the environment and people

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Barron, E. S., Chaudhary, R. P., Carvalho Ribeiro, S., Gilman, E., Hess, J., Hilborn, R., Katz, E., Kigonya, R., Masski, H., Mesa Castellanos, L. I., Mograbi, P. J., Nayak, P. K., Queiroz, H., Sidorovich, A., Silvano, R. A. M., Zeng, Y., Djagoun, C., and Danner, M. C. (2022). Chapter 3: Status of and trends in the use of wild species and its implications for wild species, the environment and people. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (517 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451322>

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Chapter 4 Chapter 4: The drivers of the sustainable use of wild species

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Balachander, G., Halmy, M. W. A., Parlee, B., Biggs, D., Chatakonda, M., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Cormier-Salem, M-C., Dasgupta, R., Devkota, S., Diniz, J., Elfaki, A., Hiwasaki, L., Lichtenstein, G., Richter, A., Shah, M. A., Shanley, P., Shrestha, U. B., Lee, T. M., Bayarbaatar, B., and Kieling, D. (2022). Chapter 4: The drivers of the sustainable use of wild species. In: Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (403 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451494>

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Chapter 5 Chapter 5: Future scenarios of sustainable use of wild species

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Gasalla, M., Tittensor, D. P., Kok, K., Archer, E., Borokini, I., Halouani, G., Matias, D. M., Mbiba, M., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Pacheco, P., Fabricius, C., and Kieling, D. (2022). Chapter 5: Future scenarios of sustainable use of wild species. In Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (146 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451922>

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6: Policy options for governing sustainable use of wild species

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Park, M. S., Hicks, C. C., Wynberg R., Mosig Reidl, P., Dhyani S., Islas, C. A., Raab, K., Avila-Foucat, V. S., Parma, A., Kolding, J., Shkaruba, A., Skandrani, Z., and Danner, M. C. (2022). Chapter 6: Policy options for governing sustainable use of wild species. In Thematic Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (182 pages). Fromentin, J. M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M. C., Hallosserie, A., and Kieling, D. (eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6452037>

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VI. Values Assessment

Full report Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

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IPBES (2022). Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (784 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522522>

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Summary for Policy Makers Summary for Policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

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IPBES (2022). Summary for Policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (37 pages). Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., González-Jiménez, D., Anderson, C. B., Athayde, S., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Martin, A., Mwampamba, T. H., Nakangu, B., O'Farrell, P., Raymond, C. M., Subramanian, S. M., Termansen, M., Van Noordwijk, M., and Vatn, A. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522392>

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: The role of the values of nature and valuation for addressing the biodiversity crisis and navigating towards more just and sustainable futures

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Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., Lliso, B., Monroy, A. S., Guibrunet, L., Anderson, C. B., Athayde, S., Barton, D. N., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Martin, A., Mwampamba, T. H., Nakangu, B., O'Farrell, P., Raymond, C. M., Subramanian, S. M., Termansen, M., Van Noordwijk, M., Vatn, A., Contreras, V., and González-Jiménez, D. (2022). Chapter 1: The role of the values of nature and valuation for addressing the biodiversity crisis and navigating towards more just and sustainable futures. In: Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (39 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Michael, C., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6418971>

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Chapter 2 Chapter 2: Conceptualizing the diverse values of nature and their contributions to people

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Anderson, C. B., Athayde, S., Raymond, C. M., Vatn, A., Arias, P., Gould, R. K., Kenter, J., Muraca, B., Sachdeva, S., Samakov, A., Zent, E., Lenzi, D., Murali, R., Amin, A., and Cantú-Fernández, M. (2022). Chapter 2: Conceptualizing the diverse values of nature and their contributions to people. In: Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (125 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Michael, C., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6493134>

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Chapter 3 Chapter 3: The potential of valuation

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Termansen, M., Jacobs, S., Mwampamba, T. H., Ahn, S., Castro, A., Dendoncker, N., Ghazi, H., Gundimeda, H., Huambachano, M., Lee, H., Mukherjee, N., Nemogá, G. R., Palomo, I., Pandit, R., Schaafsma, M., Ngouhou, J., Choi, A., Filyushkina, A., Hernández-Blanco, M., Contreras, V., and González-Jiménez, D. (2022). Chapter 3: The potential of valuation. In: Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (170 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Michael, C., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521298>

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Chapter 4 Chapter 4: Value expression in decision-making

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Barton, D. N., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Lazos, E., Van Noordwijk, M., Engel, S., Girvan, A., Hahn, T., Leimona, B., Lele, S., Niamir, A., Özkaynak, B., Pawlowska-Mainville, A., Muradian, R., Ungar, P., Aydin, C., Iranah, P., Nelson, S., Cantú-Fernández, M., and González-Jiménez, D. (2022). Chapter 4: Value expression in decision-making. In: Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (141 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Michael, C., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522261>

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Chapter 5 Chapter 5: The role of diverse values of nature in visioning and transforming towards just and sustainable futures

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Martin, A., O'Farrell, P., Kumar, R., Eser, U., Faith, D.P., Gomez-Baggethun, E., Harmackova, Z., Horcea-Milcu, A.I., Merçon, J., Quaas, M., Rode, J., Rozzi, R., Sitas, N., Yoshida, Y., Ochieng, T.N., Koessler, A.K., Lutti, N., Mannetti, L., and Arroyo-Robles, G. (2022). Chapter 5: The role of diverse values of nature in visioning and transforming towards just and sustainable futures. In: Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (126 pages). Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Michael, C., Baptiste, B., and González-Jiménez, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522326>

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6: Policy options and capacity development to operationalize the inclusion of diverse values of nature in decision-making

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Chapter 1 Chapter 1: Assessing a planet in transformation: Rationale and approach of the IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Service

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Chapter 2.1 Chapter 2.1. Status and Trends – Drivers of Change

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Chapter 2.2 Chapter 2.2. Status and Trends – Nature

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Chapter 6 Chapter 6. Options for Decision Makers

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